

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CHANGES IN THE REFERENCE VALUES OF MEDICINAL PRODUCTS INCLUDED IN ANNEX No. 2 TO POSITIVE DRUG LIST IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

The Positive Drug List introduces the first rules for including drugs in the payment system with public funds in Bulgaria.

In order to be able to allocate limited budgetary resources in the most effective and fair way and according to the profitability of new drugs, the regulatory institutions that are responsible for pricing and inclusion of drugs for payment with public funds have the greatest need for pharmacoeconomic evaluations.

For medicinal products included in the Positive Drug List, the National Health Insurance Fund negotiates with the holders of the authorizations for use or with their authorized representatives discounts on the packaging value.

The purpose of the survey is to study and analyze the changes made in the reference values of the medicinal products included in Annex No. 2 to Positive Drug List in Bulgaria for the period 2016-2020.

The analysis of the data shows a significant increase in the costs for the National Health Insurance Fund, based on reports, for medicinal products used in the treatment of diseases in the conditions of hospital medical care, included in the study application.

Keywords: reference value, medicinal products, Positive Drug List, National Health Insurance Fund, public funds.

Introduction:

The financing and regulation of the supply of medicines has a strong impact on health outcomes and the financial protection of individuals. An important challenge for all countries is the managed introduction of new and expensive health technologies, such as drug therapy, medical devices and procedures. [2, p.9]

In Bulgaria, the system for reference pricing and payment of medicines with public funds began with the creation of the National Health Insurance Fund, which actually started functioning in 2000.

The pricing processes and the corresponding preparation of the Positive Drug List (PDL), according to which the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) pays for drugs for home treatment, were introduced for the first time at the end of 2003, after the NHIF realized an overspending of funds for medicines for home treatment of BGN 100 million [2, p.14]

The first rules for the inclusion of medicines in the system of payment with public funds, as well as the regulation of the publication of lists of medicines on the website of the NHIF, are introduced with the Positive Drug List.

The purpose of its introduction is to end the existing practice in the NHIF in 2002, when the list of drugs on the NHIF's website was updated 33 times, due to the continuous inclusion of new medicinal products, leading to overspending of BGN 100 million in the NHIF. [1]

In order to be able to allocate limited budgetary resources in the most effective and fair way and accord-

ing to the profitability of new drugs, the regulatory institutions that are responsible for pricing and inclusion of drugs for payment with public funds have the greatest need for pharmacoeconomic evaluations.

The National Council on Prices and Reimbursement of Medicinal Products (NSCRMP) under the Minister of Health decides which drugs are to be included in the PDL and determines which are to be reimbursed under the mandatory health insurance and which are to be paid from the state budget.

The Council makes an assessment of efficacy, and in the presence of data on therapeutic effectiveness and/or the cost-result ratio is value-ineffective, they are included in the corresponding annex of PDL with an obligation to follow up the effect of the therapy. [15]

The Law on Health Insurance provides funds for the NHIF to be used to pay for medical activities, including the provision of medicinal products and medical devices for them, as defined in the law on the budget of the NHIF for the relevant calendar year. The NHIF pays for the provision of certain types of medical assistance, and the Minister of Health determines by regulation a list of diseases for the home treatment of which the NHIF fully or partially pays medicinal products, medical devices and dietary foods for special medical purposes. For the medicinal products included in the PDL, the NHIF negotiates with the holders of the authorizations for use or with their authorized representatives, discounts on the packaging value. The law provides for the inclusion of medicinal products intended for the treatment of malignant diseases in the conditions

of hospital medical care, which the NHIF pays beyond the value of the medical activities performed.

The Positive Drug List contains a total of 4 annexes. In three of the annexes, medicinal products are included, classified depending on the reimbursing institution, and in Annex 4 the prices according to Art. 261a, para. 1 of the Law on medicinal products in human medicine by elements. [4, p.119]

In Annex № 2 of the PDL, medicinal products are included, paid for from the budget of the medical institutions under Art. 5 of the Law on Medical Institutions, from the budget of medical institutions with state and/or municipal participation under Art. 9 and 10 of the Law on Medical Institutions.

The medicinal products in this annex have a reimbursement level of 100% for diseases according to the Summary of Product Characteristics of the Marketing Authorization. Only for medicinal products intended for the treatment of oncological diseases are assigned corresponding ICD codes.

The purpose of the survey is to study and analyze the changes made in the reference values of the medicinal products included in Annex No. 2 to Positive Drug List in Bulgaria for the period 2016-2020.

Methodology:

The following research methods were used:

- Documentary method - based on official annual reports on the activity of the National Health Insurance Fund, annual reports on the activity of the National Council on Prices and Reimbursement of Medicinal Products, scientific publications on the issue;

- Economical analysis;
- Comparative analysis;

- Statistical methods – analysis of the dynamics of the phenomena, tabular and graphic analyzes to visualize the obtained results.

Analysis of the results

Medicinal products paid by the NHIF, outside the value of the clinical pathway, included in Annex No. 2 to PLS.

The prescription and administration of medicinal products for the treatment of malignant diseases is carried out in compliance with the regulations established in the Law on Health Insurance, the Law on Medicinal Products in Human Medicine, Ordinance No. 4 on the terms and conditions for prescribing and dispensing medicinal products and the National Framework Agreement for the medical activities, standards introduced in the approved pharmaco-therapeutic manuals under Art. 259, para. 1, item 4 of the Medical Act, adopted respectively with: Ordinance No. 3 of September 19, 2019 for the adoption of a pharmaco-therapeutic manual for clinical hematology; Ordinance No. 10 of October 10, 2019 for the adoption of pharmaco-therapeutic guidelines for pediatric clinical hematology and oncology; Ordinance No. 11 of October 17, 2019 for the adoption of a pharmaco-therapeutic guide in medical oncology. [5]

External reference pricing, price revision, internal referencing in one INN (international non-proprietary name) are measures successfully implemented by almost all countries in Europe, but they alone are not sufficient to contain costs. In Bulgaria, these measures lead to saving of public resources, the main reason being the reduction of the reference value for (defined daily dose) DDD or entry of the first generic or biosimilar product into the INN. The reduction of the reference value varies widely.[16, p.165-166]

Table 1.

**Reduction and increase of the reference values for DDD by INN
of medicinal products included in Annex No. 2 of the PDL**

Years	Reduction of the reference value for DDD by INN		Total reduction of the value paid by the NHIF (in BGN)		Increasing the reference value for DDD by INN	
	number of INNs	%	in BGN	reasons	number	reasons
2016	39 INNs out of a total of 103 INNs	0.04% to 39.63%	4,661,394	in the case of 37 INNs, this is due to a reduction in the price of MP belonging to the respective INN	7 INN	due to the exclusion of MP from Annex No. 2 of the PDL
				at 2 INNs it is due to inclusion of the first generic product during the reporting period		
2017	56 INNs out of a total of 102 INNs	0.04% to 69.99%	7,942,088	reduction of the price of medicinal products bearing the reference value in 45 INN	6 INN BGN 999,061	
				inclusion of a new medicinal product in 1 INN		
				inclusion of first generic medicinal product in 4 INN		
2018	53 INNs out of a total of 110 INNs	0.01% to 80.51%	9,492,370	price reduction as a result of external price referencing at 44 INN		
				inclusion of a new medicinal product at 2 INN		
				inclusion of first generic medicinal product in 7 INN		
2019	51 INNs out of a total of 116 INNs			inclusion of a new medicinal product at 4 INN		
				inclusion of first generic medicinal product at 2 INN		
				price reduction as a result of external price referencing at 45 INN		
2020	44 INNs out of a total of 153 INNs			inclusion of a new medicinal product at 2 INN		
				reduction of the price of a medicinal product as a result of the external price referencing - at 42 INN		

Sources: Annual reports on the activity of the NHIF for 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020 and Annual reports on the activity of the NCPRMP for 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020.

As is clear from table 1, for the period 01.01.2016 - 31.12.2016 (as a result of the inclusion of medicinal products and price changes in 39 INNs out of a total of 103 INNs, the reference value for DDD has decreased. Of these, in 37 INNs, this was due to a reduction in the price of drugs belonging to the respective INN, while in 2 INNs, it was due to the inclusion of the first generic

product during the reporting period. The reduction of the reference value is within the limits of 0.04% to 39.63%.

In total, the value paid by the NHIF decreased by BGN 4,661,394 as a result of the reduction of the reference value for DDD.

For 7 INNs, an increase in the reference value was found due to the exclusion of MP from Annex No. 2 to PDL.

For 2017, out of the analyzed 102 INNs, in 56 INNs a change in the reference value for DDD was found, which was reflected in a total reduction of the value paid by the NHIF by BGN 6,943,027. The change in the DDD reference value is due to various factors and is distributed as follows:

- reduction of the price of medicinal products bearing the reference value in 45 INN;
- inclusion of a new medicinal product in 1 INN;
- inclusion of the first generic medicinal product in 4 INNs;
- exclusion of medicinal products in 6 INN;

Within the limits of 0.04% to 69.99% is the reduction of the reference value for DDD. In total, the amount paid by the NHIF decreased by BGN 7,942,088 as a result of the lowering of the reference value for DDD. In the case of 6 INNs during the reporting period, an increase in the reference value of DDD was found due to the exclusion of medicinal products from Annex No.2 to PDL. As a result, the amount paid by the NHIF increased by BGN 999,061.

The analysis assessed the impact of the change in the reference value for DDD, which reflects on the value of a final package, calculated on the basis of a reference value, respectively on the value that is paid by the NHIF for final packaging according to MP included in the relevant INN.

During the period 01.01.2018-31.12.2018 BGN 9,492,370 is the reduction of the value paid by the NHIF, determined on the basis of the final packages paid for the period of validity of the changed reference value for DDD. Reference value for DDD has decreased to 53 INN from a total of 110 INN, which is due to:

- price reduction as a result of the external price referencing at 44 INN;
- inclusion of a new medicinal product at 2 INN;
- inclusion of the first generic medicinal product in 7 INNs.

The reduction of the reference value is in the range of 0.01% to 80.51%.

The inclusion of generic medicinal products in the INN Trantuzumab has led to a decrease in the value of a package, calculated on the basis of the reference value for DDD, by 27.04%, as a result of which the value paid by the NHIF has decreased by BGN 1,660,683.

In the analysis for the period 01.01.2019-31.12.2019, the reference value for DDD decreased to 51 INNs out of a total of 116 INNs, which is due to:

- inclusion of a new medicinal product at 4 INN;
- inclusion of the first generic medicinal product at 2 INN
- price reduction as a result of the external price referencing at 45 INN.

In 2020, after an analysis, it was found that the reference value for DDD/therapeutic course decreased at 44 INNs out of a total of 153 INNs. This is due to:

- inclusion of a new medicinal product - at 2 INN;
- reduction of the price of a medicinal product as a result of the external price referencing - at 42 INN.

As a result of the inclusion of another biosimilar medicinal product, there is a significant reduction in the reference value for DDD/therapeutic course, respectively in the value of a package, calculated on the basis of a reference value in: INN Bevacizumab - by 23.00%; INN Trastuzumab – by 15.00%.

The decrease in the price of medicinal products, due to a lower producer price in the reference countries, has had a significant impact on the reduction of the reference value for DDD/therapeutic course in: INN Doxorubicin - with 65.00%; INN Cariprazine - with 49.03%; INN Azacitidine - with 32.45%.

The increase in the price of medicinal products bearing the reference value has a negative impact on the reference value for DDD/therapeutic course. As a result, it has increased - 2 INN: Mitoxantrone, Mycobacterium bovis BCG.

From table 1, we observe an increasing trend in the reduction of the reference value for DDD according to INN until 2019 in relative share and in BGN.

As a result of international referencing, the prices of medicines included in Annex No.2 to PDL are reduced. This, on the one hand, may lead to a reduction in the costs of the NHIF, but on the other hand, it gives grounds for the license holders permission to apply for the exclusion of the products from the PDL.

From the analysis of the data, it is clear that there was an increase in the reference values for a defined daily dose by international non-proprietary name of medicinal products included in Annex No. 2 to PDL in 2016 at 6 INN and in 2017 at 7 INN.

The transitional and final provisions of the NHIF Budget Law for 2019 introduce changes to the Health Insurance Law, the Law on Medicinal Products in Human Medicine, the Law on Medical Facilities, the Health Law, etc. regarding new payment mechanisms for medicinal products in the following directions:

The scope of the medicinal products included in the package guaranteed by the budget of the NHIF is being expanded. In addition to the medicinal products used in hospital medical care for the treatment of malignant diseases, medicinal products for life-threatening hemorrhages and urgent operative and invasive interventions for patients with congenital coagulopathies are also included in the conditions of hospital medical care, which at this stage are financed with funds from the budget of the Ministry of Health. At the same time, the range of products to be negotiated is specified. For the first time, the mechanisms guaranteeing the predictability and sustainability of the NHIF budget are being regulated. [5]

Part of the cost control mechanism that applies in 2019 is the negotiation by the NHIF of discounts for all medicinal products from the Positive Drug List, for which the value paid from the budget of the NHIF is calculated by grouping, in which medicinal products of other marketing authorization holders, the NHIF and the holders of authorizations for use do not participate use or their authorized representatives annually conduct a mandatory centralized negotiation of discounts (with the exception of generic and biosimilar medicinal products). [3, p.14]

Negotiating this discount is a condition for payment of the treatment with these medicinal products by the NHIF.

Figure 1. Expenditure for the NHIF on the basis of reports, for medicinal products under Annex No. 2 for malignant diseases and life-threatening hemorrhages and emergency operative and invasive interventions for patients with congenital coagulopathies in the conditions of hospital medical care

Source: Annual reports on the activity of the NHIF for 2017, 2018 and 2019.

Figure 1 shows the significant increase in costs for the NHIF on the basis of reports, for medicinal products used in the treatment of malignancies and diseases, from 2019 and life-threatening haemorrhages and urgent operative and invasive interventions of patients with congenital coagulopathies in the setting of hospital medical care for the period 2016-2019 with 74.98%.

Therapeutic approaches established in medical practice, including the use of innovative medicinal products representing personalized target therapy, ensure a better therapeutic response and have an impact on the duration and quality of life of patients. The inclusion in the Positive drug list of orphan drugs for the treatment of rare diseases, in which the technology of creating the medicinal product is expensive, determines a high value per course of treatment for one patient. Both trends lead to a significant increase in the costs of the NHIF. [8]

The reported growth in oncological medicinal products requires a detailed examination of the place of the specific medicinal products in the lines of therapy for the disease for which it is intended, the therapeutic courses, number of treatment cycles, as well as adherence to established standards in the treatment of patients with oncological and onco-hematological diseases, according to the product summary. The NHIF should strictly adhere to the consensus and pharmacotherapeutic guidelines in which the health technology is included (national, European or international). [7]

The increase in the costs of the NHIF for medicinal products used in the treatment of a relatively equal number of patients with malignant diseases is largely due to the deletion of products with lower prices and the inclusion of new ones with significantly higher prices.

CONCLUSION:

Funds for health care in general are limited. Most of the resources are allocated to finance hospital care.

There are fewer funds allocated for activities in outpatient care and especially for those related to health promotion and integrated disease prevention. A common phenomenon for most European countries is the increase in drug costs, which is an important factor in increasing pressure on overall health care costs.

The downward trend in prices is positive from the point of view of payment with public funds and public expenditure, but in the long term it may generate not only a shortage of medicinal products on the market, but also a future increase in the prices of those medicinal products whose marketing authorization holders have managed to resist and keep their products on the market, thus becoming monopolists.

From the analysis of the data, it is evident a significant increase in the costs of the NHIF based on reports, for medicinal products used in the treatment of malignant diseases in the conditions of hospital medical care included in Annex No 2 to PDL for the period 2016-2019 with 74.98%.

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